

Impact of Increasing Population on Economic Development and Well Being of Developing Nations

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Abstract:

This review explores the intricate relationship between population growth and economic development in developing nations, emphasizing the diverse effects on overall well-being. While some scholars, such as Easterlin (1967), argue against a consistent correlation between population growth and per capita income, others, including Koduru et al. (2016), highlight positive economic impacts stemming from population expansion. The literature indicates that population dynamics significantly influence social factors, including education, mental health, and resource allocation. This review aims to synthesize existing research on the dual impact of population growth on economic development and well-being, addressing key gaps in the literature. A proposed research framework is introduced to investigate these relationships and the mediating role of economic development in enhancing well-being. This framework aims to guide future studies and inform policymakers, facilitating sustainable development and improved quality of life in the context of rapid population growth.

Keywords: *Increasing population in developing nations affects economic development, healthcare access, education quality, and poverty levels*

1. Introduction

The intricate relationship between population growth and economic development has been a focal point of research, especially in the context of developing nations. As these countries navigate the complexities of rapid population increases, understanding the multifaceted effects on economic progress and overall well-being becomes paramount. Previous literature presents a diverse array of perspectives on this issue. For instance, while some scholars like Easterlin (1967) argue that the correlation between population growth and per capita income is not straightforward, others, such as Koduru et al. (2016), highlight the positive impact of population expansion on economic growth in countries like India. Additionally, concerns arise regarding the implications of population dynamics on social factors, such as mental health, education, and resource allocation. This review aims to synthesize existing literature on the population's impact on economic development and well-being, ultimately proposing a comprehensive research framework to address existing gaps and guide future studies.

2. Objectives

- 1.To assess the review of literature on of population impact of increase in population on economic development and well-being in developing nations.
- 2.To develop a positive proposed research framework on impact of increase in population on economic development and well-being in developing nations for future research.

3. Review of literature

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Easterlin, R. A. (1967), tested the link between population growth rates and per capita income does not support any consistent conclusion, even though a straightforward two-variable comparison may mask

the genuine relationship. All of this does not imply that rise in per capita income, both historically and today, would have been the same had population growth rates been noticeably greater or lower. However, it's likely that oversimplified conclusions about the relationship between population growth and economic development exist, or that no single generalization can account for nations with growth rates, densities, and income levels as diverse as those of today's less developed regions. It is obvious that a deeper investigation into the real experiences of nations, both past and present, is needed.

Koduru, et al. (2016), demonstrated that India's economic progress was positively impacted by its population expansion. Additionally, we can see that the Corruption Perception Index, Unemployment, and Population Growth have all provided an explanation. This indicates that the GDP increases by 3.383108 units for every unit increase in population. This demonstrates that India's economic progress is positively impacted by population expansion.

Peterson, (2017), examined the relationships between population growth, per capital output growth, and overall economic growth over the past 200 years using historical data. While high population growth in low-income countries may impede their progress, low population growth in high-income countries is likely to cause social and economic concerns. Although many people oppose it, international migration may be able to help correct these inequities. It suggests that slower population growth and less migration could be factors in rising national and international economic inequality, based on economic analysis of inequality.

Singh, A. K. (2021) analysed the theoretical considerations regarding the expected effects—positive or negative—of increased population growth on economic development. The article examines the demographic shifts that have occurred historically during the past 200 years in both industrialized and emerging nations, focusing on China and India. It also analyzes the causes that have contributed to these changes. There is also an analysis of how the results may affect population control strategies. The relationship between the fall in fertility and socioeconomic progress is becoming increasingly apparent. Demographers generally agree that the focus of fertility reduction programs should be on individuals' free choices rather than coercion, and that these policies should be developed within the framework of a much larger program for social, economic, and political growth. The relative importance of the positive and negative incentives in this scenario is constrained.

Dao, (2011), tested the interaction variables in light of the severe degree of multicollinearity among explanatory variables, found that per capita GDP growth linearly depends on population growth, the old dependency ratio, the mortality rate, and the interactions between population growth and both the young and old dependency ratios, between population growth and whether or not the rate of population growth is less than 1.2 percent per year, and the interaction term between the young dependency ratio and whether or not the rate of population growth is less than 1.2 percent per year.

4. Impact of increase in population on well-being of the developing nations

Income, mental and physical health, education, social connections, employment, discrimination, government regulations, and local circumstances all have an impact on individuals' well-being. Well-being encompasses both physical and mental health as part of a comprehensive approach to health promotion and illness prevention (**Livingston, et al. 2022**)

Kelley, A.C. (1996), underlined the negative impact on economic growth of moving resources from productivity-enhancing equipment and factories to education and human capital, which are expected to have lower rates of return.¹ Empirical investigations have demonstrated the potentially enormous costs of schooling required simply to maintain educational standards. Many Third World countries appear to face a hard undertaking in expanding educational coverage and levels.

Ruttan, V.W. (1996), investigated a number of agricultural, resource, and environmental concerns that will influence the agricultural sector's ability to meet the demands of population and income growth, particularly in Latin American, Asian, and African developing countries.

Panayotou, T. (1996), suggested the worry about deforestation, water scarcity, land degradation, food security, or global warming, it is widely assumed that population increase is at least somewhat responsible. Dwindling resources are shared by an ever-growing human population, which dumps

increasing amounts of garbage into limited space. Consequently, population policies are viewed as critical to resource conservation and environmental preservation.

Mason, A. (1996), assessed Three theories that underpinned the links between population and the housing sector are critical for evaluating population policy: Population growth drives up the need for a) residential land, b) houses, and c) urban infrastructure. Increased demand will result in higher prices and/or lower-quality dwellings. Meeting demand for housing and urban infrastructure will drain resources away from more growth-oriented applications, such as investment in manufacturing, undercutting development goals.

Livingston, et al., (2022), People's well-being has the capacity to influence society's overall well-being and productivity. Though it may be measured at the individual level, well-being is an important population result at the macro level and hence a public health concern.

5. Findings & Proposed Model

Various studies found the significant relationship between increase in population and economic growth, while some studies indicated no significant relationship between the population and economic development. Previous research indicated both positive and negative impact of the increase in the population on wellbeing of the nation. However, there is a huge research gap which encompasses the impact of the increase in population on both economic development and well-being of the developing nations.

Based on above review of literature the following research framework has been developed which test the relationship between the impact of increase in population on economic development and well-being in developing nations. Further testing the mediating impact of the economic development between the impact of increase in population and well-being of the developing nations.

Figure 1. Proposed Research Model (Framework)

6. Conclusion

The examination of the literature reveals a complex interplay between population growth, economic development, and well-being in developing nations. While some studies affirm the beneficial aspects of population increases on economic indicators, others caution against potential adverse effects, highlighting the need for a nuanced understanding. The research also indicates significant gaps in our knowledge, particularly regarding the dual impact of population growth on economic development and well-being. To address these gaps, the proposed research framework seeks to explore these relationships more deeply, considering the mediating effects of economic development on well-being. This framework not only sets the stage for future empirical investigations but also aims to inform policymakers in developing nations about the implications of population dynamics on economic and social outcomes. By bridging these gaps, we can enhance our understanding of how to harness population growth for sustainable development and improved quality of life.

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